

Obtaining Equilibrium Distribution from $dE = \text{Number} \cdot dT$ Implies the Kaniadakis Distribution is a non-Equilibrium One

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In (1), we used the approach $E = \text{Number} \cdot T \rightarrow dE = \text{Number} \cdot dT$ ((1)) ($E = \text{energy}$, $T = \text{temperature}$) and found the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. In particular, we used:

$$\text{Number} = \frac{\int C(T) e^{-E/T} p(ei/T) C_1 \sqrt{e} de}{\int C(T) c_1 \sqrt{e} de} \quad ((2))$$

Here $p(ei/T)$ is unnormalized, $C(T)$ is the normalization constant and one works in 3-dimensions hence $\int dp dp^2 = c_1 \sqrt{e} de$.

We then used $T \rightarrow T + dT$ in Number ((2)) and equated the coefficient of dT to 0. This led to a unique solution, namely the Maxwell-Boltzmann one, with no assumption of maximization of arrangements, entropy or reaction balance.

If one steps back, however, it seems that the solution which yields $dT = 0$ must be special given that it is unique. If one considers a set of normalized probabilities $\{ C(T)p(ei/T) \}$ then it is possible to have many sets add to one and still satisfy $\sum_i e_i C(T) p(ei/T) = E_{ave}$ ((3)) for a particular value of E_{ave} . $p(ei/T) = \exp(-ei/T)$ is one math function, while $p_1(ei/T) = g(ei/T)$ is another. Note: $g(ei/T)$ has some specific math form and satisfies ((3)) for the specific E_{ave} chosen. One most likely only knows the numerical values of $g(ei/T)$, but the fact that they differ from $\exp(-ei/T)$ means that one is dealing with a different math function.

Even though $\exp(-ei/T)$ and $g(ei/T)$ yield E_{ave} for a single E_{ave} (and corresponding T), if one changes $T \rightarrow T + dT$, one should obtain different $E_{ave}(\text{new})$ values for each as $\exp(-ei/T)$ and $g(ei/T)$ are different functions.

Now ((1)) holds in general, but different $p(ei/T)$ functions should yield a different value for Number. Experimentally, however, one may measure ((1)) and should find a single unique number. Thus, one seeks a unique solution to having the coefficient of dT from ((2)) be 0. The math approach of $T \rightarrow T + dT$ with the coefficient of dT does lead to a unique (special solution) without one knowing offhand why the solution is unique. This suggests that this probability distribution may in fact be the special one which appears in nature and in fact, $\exp(-ei/T)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution does arise. (We have also shown that one may $\sum_i e_i p(ei/T)$ power q with the same approach and obtain the Tsallis distribution.)

We first link this idea to Shannon maximization of entropy or reaction balance results and show that they coincide if $p(ei) = \exp(-ei/T)$. We then apply the ideas to the Kaniadakis distribution and show that it does not lead to a 0 coefficient of dT and suggest that this may mean that the distribution is not an equilibrium one, at least in the 3D nonrelativistic case.

dE= Number * dT Approach to Finding a Distribution

We used the $dE = \text{Number} * dT$ approach to find both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions in previous notes (1). The idea is that one considers $p(e_i/T)$ as the distribution and allows e_i to range from 0 to infinite which is a standard approximation. This means that:

$$E_{ave} = T * \left\{ \sum_i \int C(T) e/T p(e_i/T) C_1 \sqrt{e} de \right\} / \left\{ \sum_i \int C(T) c_1 \sqrt{e} de \right\}$$

$$= \text{Number} * T \quad ((4))$$

Here we have used 3-dimensions in the nonrelativistic approximation $e = pp/2m$ i.e.

$$Pp dp 4*3.14 = c_1 \sqrt{e} de \quad ((5))$$

In the relativistic case: $-ee + pp = -momo$ ($c=1$) ((6)) so:

$$Pp dp 4*3.14 = c_2 e \sqrt{ee-moo} de \quad ((6))$$

In (1), we explicitly showed that the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ holds in the nonrelativistic 3D case using this approach. In ((4)), $C(T)$ is the normalization.

In (1), for the nonrelativistic case, we found a unique solution by allowing $T \rightarrow T+dT$ in the expression for Number. In other words, we found a specific $p(e_i/T) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ which may be compared to experiment and found to match.

It is known that for a given E_{ave} , one may find various sets of $p(e_i/T)$ which satisfy:

$$\sum_i C(T) p(e_i/T) e_i = E_{ave} \quad ((7))$$

These in principle represent different functions because $\exp(-e_i/T)$ gives rise to a certain numerical set of $p(e_i/T)$ for a specific E_{ave} . Other numerical sets of $p(e_i/T)$ should represent different functions. Even though these allow for multiple solutions of $p(e_i/T)$ for a given E_{ave} (and corresponding T), changing $T \rightarrow T+dT$ would lead to different values for Number in ((4)), and only one value of number matches experimental results. As a result, one should have an approach which yields a unique probability distribution which the $dE = \text{Number} * dT$ approach does.

Interestingly, one usually uses a maximization of arrangements or entropy subject to a priori constraints to obtain a unique probability distribution. In the reaction balance approach

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ if } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \quad ((8))$$

yields $\exp(-e_i/T)$, but one assumes a uniform distribution for any $e_i + e_j = \text{specific } E_1 \text{ value}$. This is a least information solution which is linked to maximization of entropy. The $dE = \text{Number} * dT$ approach does not assume minimum information or maximization of entropy, but is simply a computational approach which gives rise to a unique solution which is assumed to be the experimental one. We now consider the approach in more detail

Mapping the $dE = \text{Number} * dT$ Approach to Shannon's Entropy

In ((4)) one may allow $y = e_i/T$ so:

$$e_i / (T+dT) \rightarrow e_i/T - 1/T y dT \quad \text{and} \quad dp/dT = - y dp/dy 1/T \quad ((9))$$

Considering ((4)) one has the coefficient of dT (within an $\int p(e) de$ integral) set to 0 as

$$y dp/dy - y p - dp/dy y (E/T) = 0 \quad ((10)) \quad E/T = \text{Number}$$

One may integrate the first term by parts and so if the numbers are fine (as is shown in (1)), then

$$p = \exp(-y) = \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((10))$$

We now want to map ((10)) to the Shannon's maximum entropy or reaction balance result of:

$$\ln(p) = -e_i/T \quad (\text{where } p(e_i) \text{ is unnormalized}) \quad ((11))$$

$$\text{Then one has: } dp + \ln(p) dp - dp (E/T) \quad ((12))$$

Given that $dp = dp/dy (-y) dT$ one maps $-dp (E/T)$ to $dp/dy y (E/T)$, $\ln(p) dp$ to $y y dp/dy$ and so $dp = -y dp/dy 1/T$ must map to $y p$. This suggests that $dp/dy = -p$ which yields the unique Maxwell-Boltzmann solution, $p = \exp(-y)$.

Kaniadakis Case

We next consider the Kaniadakis case which yields a specific probability distribution:

$$p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized} = (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx)^{-1/k} \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((13))$$

Given that $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i p(e_i) C(T)$ traditionally for the Kaniadakis case, it does not seem possible for this distribution to lead to a coefficient of 0 for dT . We consider:

$$E = \text{Number}_1 * T \quad \text{and} \quad E = \text{Number}_2 * T \quad \text{for a gas in nature} \quad ((14))$$

We argued that the unique solution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ represents an equilibrium solution. If the Kaniadakis case does not yield a 0 coefficient, this seems to imply a nonequilibrium solution, at least in the nonrelativistic scenario which we consider.

To see the Kaniadakis situation, one may compare ((10)) with

$\ln(gp) = -e_i/T$ where p is given by ((13)) so g is explicitly known

Then:

$$\ln(g) dp + dp + \ln(p) dp - dp * \text{Number} = -dp * \text{Number} + dp - e_i/T dp = 0$$

This maps to: $-dp/dy y * \text{Number} - dp/dy y + yy dp/dy = 0$ ((15))

In this case, one should again have $dp/dy = -p$, but that is not the Kaniadakis case. As a result, we suggest that the Kaniadakis case does not lead to a 0 coefficient of dT as it is not the unique equilibrium result, but perhaps a nonequilibrium situation in the nonrelativistic case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the $E=\text{Number}*T \rightarrow dE=\text{Number} * dT$ approach with Number given by ((4)) leads to a unique probability distribution if one uses $T \rightarrow T+dT$ and sets the coefficient of dT to 0. We used this approach in (1) to find $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the 3D nonrelativistic case and so suggest that this unique solution is in fact the equilibrium one which appears in nature. We were also able to show that the Tsallis solution arises from this approach if one uses $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i p_1(e_i)^q$ where $p_1(e_i)$ is the normalized Tsallis distribution. We argue that the Kaniadakis distribution does not lead to a 0 dT coefficient in the 3D nonrelativistic case and so conclude that in such a case, it is a nonequilibrium result.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Information, Scaling and the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis Distributions (preprint, zenodo, 2026)